

CMIP5 and CMIP6 analysis over polar regions

Cécile Agosta, Christoph Kittel, Charles Amory

Cécile Agosta : LSCE, Paris-Saclay, France

Christoph Kittel : Université de Liège, Belgium

Charles Amory : IGE, Grenoble, France

IWV[ann] : integrated water vapor, annual, 1980-2004

CMIP5

Arctic (> 50°N)

CMIP6

IWV[ann] : integrated water vapor, annual, 1980-2004

CMIP5

Antarctic (< 40°S)

CMIP6

SLP[ann] : sea level pressure, annual, 1980-2004

CMIP5

Arctic (> 50°N)

CMIP6

SLP[ann] : sea level pressure, annual, 1980-2004

CMIP5

Antarctic (< 40°S)

CMIP6

Distributions of RMSE / (median RMSE)

Correlations between metrics, North

Correlations between metrics, South

Score by model

Testing different combinations

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'SLP+T850' : ['SLP[ann]', 'T850[ann]', 'IWV[ann]', 'SST[sum]', 'SIC[win]']
'Z500+T850' : ['Z500[ann]', 'T850[ann]', 'IWV[ann]', 'SST[sum]', 'SIC[win]']
'SLP+T700' : ['SLP[ann]', 'T700[ann]', 'IWV[ann]', 'SST[sum]', 'SIC[win]']
'Z500+T700' : ['Z500[ann]', 'T700[ann]', 'IWV[ann]', 'SST[sum]', 'SIC[win]']
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North

Q1 - Q2

South

Q1 - Q2

Score, South vs. North

Score, South vs. North

Gorte et al 2020 Eval. vs. Prec - Evap

GISS-E2-H

CMIP5 and CMIP6 analysis over polar regions : supplementary slides

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SIC[winter] : sea ice concentration, winter, 1980-2004

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Arctic (> 50°N)

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SIC[winter] : sea ice concentration, winter, 1980-2004

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CMIP6

SST[summer] : sea surface temperature, summer, 1980-2004

CMIP5

Arctic (> 50°N)

CMIP6

ta850[ann] : air temperature at 850 hPa, annual, 1980-2004

CMIP5

Arctic (> 50°N)

CMIP6

ta850[ann] : air temperature at 850 hPa, annual, 1980-2004

CMIP5

Antarctic (< 40°S)

CMIP6

